

Papers on Ancient Greek Linguistics

Proceedings of the Ninth International Colloquium on
Ancient Greek Linguistics
(ICAGL 9)

30 August – 1 September 2018, Helsinki

Societas Scientiarum Fennica

The Finnish Society of Sciences and Letters

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Edited by
MARTTI LEIWO, MARJA VIERROS & SONJA DAHLGREN

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Im/politeness strategies in Euripides: an approach to linguistic characterisation through qualitative data analysis

SANDRA RODRÍGUEZ PIEDRABUENA

1 Introduction

This paper explores the extent to which the typology of im/politeness strategies proposed by Brown and Levinson (1987) and House and Kasper (1981) can be applied to Classical Greek in Euripidean tragedies. The dual aim here is to pin down the linguistic realisations of each strategy regarding its distribution per character type. As a result, we can gain further insights into how these strategies work. To this end, suppliant scenes have been chosen because they provide interactions which are easy to compare as regards the character type and the context. This is so because they follow a fixed interactional pattern and have a recurring cast of characters (Kopperschmidt 1966), consisting minimally of a suppliant and a *supplicandus* (Naiden 2006). This structure involves a ‘bilateral’ supplication, in which the role of the *supplicandus* can shift to that of an opponent if his request is eventually rejected. A third character, who acts as an opponent of the suppliant (e.g. the Heralds in *E.Heracl.* and *E.Supp.*), can be added to this scheme, thus resulting in a ‘triangular’ supplication (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Triangular and bilateral supplication (Kopperschmidt 1966: 47–51)

2 Method

As already noted, the starting point of this analysis is a combined typology of im/politeness strategies proposed by Brown and Levinson (1987) and House and Kasper (1981). However, it also leverages the significant contributions of postmodern approaches to linguistic politeness (Eelen 2001; Watts 2003, Watts 2005) and cognitive approaches to the study of verbal irony (Alba Juez 1998; Athanasiadou and Colston 2017).

2.1 Corpus

The corpus includes the following suppliant scenes (with the main editions and commentaries included in brackets): *E.Heracl.* 55–287 (Pearson 1907; Wilkins 1993; Allan 2001); *E.Supp.* 110–597 (Murray 1902; Collard 1975; Morwood 2007), *E.Or.* 380–724 (Biehl 1965; Willink 1986; West 1987), *E.Andr.* 515–746 (Hyslop 1900; Lloyd 1994; Stevens 1971), *E.Hec.* 218–443; *Hec.* 726–863 (Collard 1991; Gregory 1999; Matthiessen 2010).

The participation level of each character involved in the aforesaid scenes can be gauged by the number of words and turns, as shown in Table 1. The participation level according to the coverage percentage is the proportion of words in relation to the total number of words per scene.

Table 1. Participation level per number of turns and words and per coverage percentage. The sum of percentages is not equal to 100% in all cases because choral interventions have been excluded.

Characters	Lines	No. of coded references (turns)	No. of coded words	Coverage percentage
Demophon	<i>E.Heracl.</i> 55–287	15	253	15.55%
Iolaus	<i>E.Heracl.</i> 55–287	10	432	28.04%
Copreus	<i>E.Heracl.</i> 55–287	20	526	33.84%
Adrastus	<i>E.Supp.</i> 110–597	27	403	12.38%
Aethra	<i>E.Supp.</i> 110–597	5	242	7.24%
Theseus	<i>E.Supp.</i> 110–597	44	1614	49.53%
Herald	<i>E.Supp.</i> 110–597	11	473	14.38%
Menelaus	<i>E.Or.</i> 380–724	41	520	19.97%
Orestes	<i>E.Or.</i> 380–724	39	1137	46.29%
Tyndareus	<i>E.Or.</i> 380–724	8	573	24.32%

Characters	Lines	Coded references (turns)	Coded words	Coverage percentage
Andromache	E. <i>Andr.</i> 515–746	3	136	9.28%
Menelaus	E. <i>Andr.</i> 515–746	7	488	35.11%
Molossus	E. <i>Andr.</i> 515–746	3	22	1.59%
Peleus	E. <i>Andr.</i> 515–746	8	647	44.90%
Hecuba 1	E. <i>Hec.</i> 218–443	23	631	40.13%
Odysseus	E. <i>Hec.</i> 218–443	13	370	23.89%
Polyxene	E. <i>Hec.</i> 218–443	11	417	26.67%
Agamemnon	E. <i>Hec.</i> 726–863	20	312	30.50%
Hecuba 2	E. <i>Hec.</i> 726–863	19	561	58.96%

2.2 Parameters

The approach to politeness implemented here was defined by Leech (2014: 17–18, 217) as sociopragmatic. It is a bipolar scale with plus and minus values on either side the zero-politeness zone (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Pragmalinguistic and sociopragmatic politeness scales (Leech 2014: 17–18, 217)

According to this approach, politeness strategies are evaluated in terms of sociodemographic factors such as power (vertical distance), which accounts for differences in status, distance (horizontal distance), which is the degree of familiarity in a given situation, and the cost-benefit of the implied propositional content. This approach seems to be particularly useful for the study of linguistic characterisation. It should be noted that zero-politeness can vary from language

to language. In English, an automated formula of request of the type *Could you hold on, please?* “may seem an entirely normal way to ask a stranger to hold the telephone line” (Leech 2014: 17), whereas a literal translation, for instance, into Spanish is likelier to fall outside the zero-politeness zone. Similarly, *Cari, dame el libro ese, anda* (‘Honey, give the book, come on’) would be a zero-politeness way of making a request in Spanish, whereas the corresponding zero-politeness phrase in English would be something like “*Darling, could you lend me that book?*” (Dickey 2016: 201). Leech (2014: 17) defined zero-politeness in terms of “routine politeness that does not strike one as out of the ordinary”, which is close to the idea of *politic behaviour* devised by Watts (2003, 2005). It follows, therefore, that native speakers’ intuition is key to perceiving the degree of im/politeness. In the absence of this possibility in Ancient Greek, the focus on the character type in comparable interactions can be an effective alternative for overcoming this hurdle.

The strategies analysed fall on both sides of the scale. On the one hand, a selection was made of *downgraders*, broadly understood as politeness strategies, and, on the other, *upgraders*, broadly understood as impoliteness strategies (House and Kasper 1981). The downgraders are as follows:¹

1. Hedges, such as committers, e.g. *I think, I guess, I believe, I suppose* and *in my opinion*; and downtoners (\approx understatements, Leech 2014: 147–148), e.g. *just, simply, possibly, perhaps* and *rather*. Furthermore, there are hedges relating to the felicity conditions, generally in the form of conditionals (see Heringer 1976), as in Example (1):

(1) (Strepsiadēs–Xanthias) ὦ Ξανθία, | κλίμακα λαβὼν ἕξελθε καὶ σμινύην φέρων, | κάπειτ’ ἐπαναβὰς ἐπὶ τὸ φροντιστήριον | τὸ τέγος κατάσκαπτ’, εἰ φιλεῖς τὸν δεσπότην, | ἕως ἂν αὐτοῖς ἐμβάλῃς τὴν οἰκίαν (Ar.Nu. 1485–1489).

‘Come hither, come hither, Xanthias! Come forth with a ladder and with a mattock and then mount upon the thinking-shop and dig down the roof, if you love your master, until you tumble the house upon them.’ (tr. Hickie 1853)

2. Impersonalisation. This strategy is in turn subdivided into purely gnomic expressions and agent avoiders, which are referred to here as *defocalisers*. The concept of *agent avoider* devised by House and Kasper (1981: 168) is a confusing

¹ There are other similar typologies of im/politeness strategies. See, for instance, Fraser 1980; Edmondson 1977; Holmes 1995; Caffi 1999: 881–909; Caffi 2007: 98–120. For further typologies, see Watts 2003: 185.

term since it can allude to expressions which do actually have an explicit agent, normally in the form of an indefinite (e.g. τις, ὅστις). Strictly speaking, what is avoided is not the expression of the agent but its identification (cf. Haverkate 1984: 79), especially when the referent is the speaker or the hearer. The term ‘defocaliser’ is perhaps a better description in these instances.² Given the context, the identity of the agent is generally easy to determine with little or no inference. Leech (1983: 80) provided the following example, typically uttered by a parent to a child:

(2) P: *Someone’s eaten the icing off the cake.*

C: *It wasn’t me.*

(Leech 1983: 80)

It should be observed that although C’s reaction is apparently irrelevant from a Gricean perspective, it is motivated by the easy identification of ‘someone’ with the hearer and of the whole utterance as an accusation. Leech (1983: 81–82) interpreted this example as a “small step of politeness”, without ruling out that the utterance “can easily tip over into ironic interpretation”. That is probably why *defocalisers* are somewhat less effective. The intention now is to look into how this strategy works in Greek tragedy.

3. Forewarnings and reluctance (≈ hedged performatives, Leech 1983: 139–140). These imply metacomments on a face-threatening act (FTA), two examples of which are given below:

(3) (Orestes–Tyndareus) ὦ γέρον, ἐγὼ τοι πρὸς σὲ δειμαίνω λέγειν, | ὅπου σὲ μέλλω σὴν τε λυπήσειν φρένα. | ἐγὼ δ’, ἀνόσιός εἰμι μητέρα κτανών, | ὅσιος δέ γ’ ἕτερον ὄνομα, τιμωρῶν πατρί. | ἀπελθέτω δὴ τοῖς λόγοισιν ἐκποδὸν | τὸ γῆρας ἡμῖν τὸ σόν, ὃ μ’ ἐκπλήσσει λόγου, | καὶ καθ’ ὁδὸν εἶμι: νῦν δὲ σὴν ταρβῶ τρίχα (E. Or. 544–550).

‘Old man, I am afraid to speak before you, in a matter where I am sure to grieve you to the heart. I am unholy because I killed my mother, I know it, yet holy on another count, because I avenged my father. Only let your years, which

² Haverkate (1992: 516): “the referential scope of *one* is marked for non-specificity. It may be used, therefore, as an appropriate device for suppressing the identity of the participants in the speech act. The strategy involved, which can be properly called *defocalization* should be described as a distancing technique applied by the speaker in order to minimize his/her own role or that of the hearer in the state of affairs described [...]; suppression of the speaker’s identity typically serves to mitigate assertive force”.

frighten me from speaking, set no barrier in the path of my words, and I will go forward; but now I fear your grey hairs.’ (Coleridge 1938)

(4) (Adrastus–Theseus): ἀλλ’, ὦ καθ’ Ἑλλάδ’ ἀλκιμώτατον κάρα, | ἄναξ Ἀθηνῶν, ἐν μὲν αἰσχύναις ἔχω | πίτνων πρὸς οὐδας γόνυ σὸν ἀμπίσχειν χερί, | πολιὸς ἀνὴρ τύραννος εὐδαίμων πάρος: | ὅμως δ’ ἀνάγκη συμφοραῖς εἴκειν ἐμαῖς (E.*Supp.* 163–167).

‘O king of Athens, bravest of the sons of Hellas, I am ashamed to throw myself upon the ground and clasp your knees, I a grey-haired king, blessed in days gone by; yet I must yield to my misfortunes.’ (Coleridge 1938)

The following subtypes are analysed as upgraders. 1. Overstaters. An overstater “overrepresents the reality denoted in the proposition” (House and Kasper 1981: 169) in the context of an FTA. In the following example, οὐποτ’ can be identified as an overstater:

(5) (Tyndareus–Menelaus) Ἑλένην τε, τὴν σὴν ἄλοχον, οὐποτ’ αἰνέσω | οὐδ’ ἂν προσείποιμ’ (E.*Or.* 520–521).

‘Helen, too, your own wife, I will never commend, nor would I even speak to her.’ (Coleridge 1938)

2. Intensifiers. Unlike overstaters, which modalise the utterance, intensifiers perform at the propositional level. An intensifier is an “adverbial modifier used by X to intensify certain elements of the proposition of his utterance” (House and Kasper 1981: 169):

(6) (Menelaus–Molossus) σοὶ δ’ οὐδὲν ἔχω φίλτρον, ἐπεὶ τοι | μέγ’ ἀναλώσας ψυχῆς μόριον | Τροίαν εἶλον καὶ μητέρα σὴν· | ἧς ἀπολαύων | Ἄιδην χθόνιον καταβήσῃ (E.*Andr.* 540–543).

‘I have no cause to love you since I expended a great part of my soul in capturing Troy and with it your mother. It is the benefit you derive from her that you now go down to the Underworld.’ (Kovacs 1995)

3. +Committers. They can be understood as the counterparts of committers. They are “sentence modifiers by means of which X indicates his heightened degree of commitment vis-à-vis the state of affairs referred to in the proposition” (House and Kasper 1981: 170), as in the following example:

(7) (Copreus–Iolaus) Κη. ἐγὼ δὲ τούσδε, κἄν σὺ μὴ θέλῃς, | ἄζω νομίζων
οὐπὲρ εἶς· Εὐρύσθεώς (E.Heracl. 67–68).

'I shall drag these children away, even if you're unwilling, considering them Eurystheus' property, which they are.' (Allan 2001)

It should be stressed that κἄν σὺ μὴ θέλῃς ('even if you're unwilling') works as a sort of *anti-hedge* relating to the felicity conditions: instead of a hedging strategy, such as *if you're willing, if you want*, Copreus explicitly flouts the felicity conditions, which are conversely expected to be hedged.

4. Lexical intensifiers: i.e. explicit insults (see 3.2).

5. Aggressive interrogatives. They are *non-prototypical interrogatives* (Risselada 1993: 39) in which the speaker, rather than requesting information, is doing something else. The adjacency pair system is often flouted, as the speaker usually does not even expect an answer. They can be uttered in a reproachful or indignant tone, as in the following example:

(8) (Tyndareus–Menelaus): Μενέλαε, προσφθέγγη νιν, ἀνόσιον κάρα; (E.Or. 481).

'Menelaus, are you speaking to that godless wretch?' (Coleridge 1938).

They frequently appear in clusters, thus blocking the a priori expected second term of the adjacency pair (e.g. E.Hec. 251–253; 258–263).

6. Personalisation. This is the counterpart of the impersonalisation downgrader. There is personalisation whenever the second person (σύ, σε, σοι) is stressed in the context of an FTA, instead of being avoided (impersonalisation):

(9) (Orestes–Tindareus): σύ τοι φυτεύσας θυγατέρ', ὦ γέρον, κακὴν |
ἀπώλεσάς με (E.Or. 585–586).

'You, yes! you, old man, have been my ruin by begetting a wicked daughter.' (Coleridge 1938).

It should be recalled that the label 'personalisation' is limited to the second-person reference, whereas, whenever the first person (ἐγώ, με, μοι, etc.) is used as a hedging device or, conversely, stresses an FTA, the corresponding labels are 'commiter' and '+commiter', respectively.

It goes without saying that there is no one-to-one relationship between these strategies and their linguistic realisations. It is only the overall context that determines whether a certain form should be labelled as an upgrader or

downgrader. For instance, the explicit use of ἐγώ in the context of a dispreferred second pair part would be an upgrader when stressing disagreement. There is nothing to prevent the same pronoun from appearing in the context of a praise speech act or a preferred second, in which case it should no longer be classified as an upgrader (e.g. *E.Supp.* 186).

2.3 NVivo

Just as many are the features analysed and the characters involved, so too are the intersections between the strategies and the characters. In order to overcome this difficulty, the tests were run using qualitative data analysis (QDA) software. Once the whole corpus had been coded, read through and analysed, the strategies were coded in different categories called ‘nodes’, from which the software provided an accurate tally of words and automatically generated results relating to the distribution of the proposed features among the characters. In order to code the texts using the NVivo software, they were retrieved from TLG and the aforementioned editions and commentaries were checked (See Section 2.1).

3 Data

In this section, the raw distribution of downgraders and upgraders per character type is presented. Following this, some instances that help to gain further insights into how these strategies actually work are considered.

3.1 Distribution of downgraders

3.1.1 Hedges

Table 2. Distribution of hedges per character; column percentage per no. of coded words. No. of words in brackets.

Characters	Committers	Felicity conditions	Downtoners
1. Demophon (<i>Heracl.</i>)	0%	23.53% (16)	0%
2. Iolaus (<i>Heracl.</i>)	31.01% (40)	27.94% (19)	0%
3. Copreus (<i>Heracl.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
1. Theseus (<i>Supp.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
2. Adrastus (<i>Supp.</i>)	0%	0%	20.31% (13)

Aethra (<i>Supp.</i>)	0%	0%	12.5%
3. Herald (<i>Supp.</i>)	4.65% (6)	0%	0%
1. Menelaus (<i>Or.</i>)	0%	13.24% (9)	35.94% (23)
2. Orestes (<i>Or.</i>)	21.71% (28)	0%	0%
3. Tyndareus (<i>Or.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
1. Peleus (<i>Andr.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
2. Andromache (<i>Andr.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
2. Molossus (<i>Andr.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
3. Menelaus (<i>Andr.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
1. Odysseus (<i>Hec.</i>)	30.23% (39)	0%	0%
2. Hecuba 1 (<i>Hec.</i>)	0%	35.29% (24)	0%
1. Agamemnon (<i>Hec.</i>)	12.4% (16)	0%	7.81% (5)
2. Hecuba 2 (<i>Hec.</i>)	0%	0%	23.44% (15)

In light of Table 2, it is possible to offer the following interpretation:

(1) Hedges are mainly uttered by suppliants, identified by the number 2 in the first column (i.e. Iolaus, Adrastus, Orestes, Hecuba 1 and 2). In terms of Brown and Levinson's politeness theory, suppliants have a low level of power in the interaction, that is, they are of a lower status than the addressees.

(2) Characters with a higher status who employ hedges are mainly *supplicandi* who reject suppliants, viz. Menelaus in *E.Or.* and Odysseus (no. 1 in the first column).

(3) Other characters with a higher status in the interaction who still utter hedges are Demophon, Agamemnon and the Herald in *E.Supp.* They seem to be characterised as more conciliatory characters than both their adversaries and their counterparts in other plays, viz. Theseus, Peleus, Copreus, Tyndareus and Menelaus in *Andr.*, who do not use hedges at all. These are especially hostile characters who give rise to conflict in the plot. It is also noteworthy that three of these hostile characters are portrayed as either young (Theseus) or old (Peleus and Tyndareus).

3.1.2 Impersonalisation

The two different strategies of impersonalisation seem to work in the language of Greek tragedy as described above (see Section 2.2): there is a scale of

impersonalisation in which defocalisers are at the lower end. Let us consider the following example in which Demophon alludes to Copeus with an indefinite *τις* that does not minimise the FTA:

(10) ὄμως δὲ καὶ νῦν μὴ τρέσης ὅπως σέ τις | σὺν παισὶ βωμοῦ τοῦδ’
ἀποσπάσει βίᾳ (E.*Herac.* 248).

‘Still even now do not be afraid that anyone will tear you | and the children from this altar by force.’ (Allan 2001)

Thus, Bond (1981: 260 *ad* E.*HF* 748) remarks that “*τις* referring obliquely to a definite person (*LSJ*, A3) is primarily menacing”.³ In this vein, Allan (2001: 152) points out that “*τις* can also refer threateningly to the person addressed [...]. The word’s vagueness and ambiguity can be exploited for ironic effect: cf. *IT* 548; *Ant.* 751.”

Table 3. Distribution of impersonalisation per character; column percentage per no. of coded words. No. of words in brackets.

Characters	Defocalisers	Gnomic expressions
1. Demophon (<i>Herac.</i>)	6.36% (15)	0.83% (5)
2. Iolaus (<i>Herac.</i>)	0%	0%
3. Copeus (<i>Herac.</i>)	4.66% (11)	0%
1. Theseus (<i>Supp.</i>)	23.31% (55)	13.46% (81)
2. Adrastus (<i>Supp.</i>)	0%	8.8% (53)
Aethra (<i>Supp.</i>)	21.61% (51)	2.66% (16)
3. Herald (<i>Supp.</i>)	13.14% (31)	23.26% (140)
1. Menelaus (<i>Or.</i>)	27.12% (64)	12.29% (74)
2. Orestes (<i>Or.</i>)	0%	7.81% (47)
3. Tyndareus (<i>Or.</i>)	0%	1.33% (8)
1. Peleus (<i>Andr.</i>)	0%	5.81% (35)
2. Andromache (<i>Andr.</i>)	0%	0%
2. Molossus (<i>Andr.</i>)	0%	0%
3. Menelaus (<i>Andr.</i>)	0%	9.47% (57)

³ See also S.*Ant.* 751; *Ai.* 1138. Finglass (2007: 514) identifies further parallels in S.*El.* 1410; *Ar.Ran.* 554, 606, 664; *Theocr.* 5.120, 122; E.*fr.* 253.2.

1. Odysseus (<i>Hec.</i>)	3.81% (9)	4.32% (26)
2. Hecuba 1 (<i>Hec.</i>)	0%	2.33% (14)
1. Agamemnon (<i>Hec.</i>)	0%	0%
2. Hecuba 2 (<i>Hec.</i>)	0%	7.64% (46)

The following conclusions can be drawn from the data shown in Table 3:

(1) There are more instances of gnomic expressions than of defocalisers. Gnostic expressions do not seem to have much bearing on the linguistic characterisation of the character types involved in suppliant scenes if we just rely on their distribution. *Gnomai* are a constituting element of tragedy and the argument structure,⁴ and are uttered by any type of character in the corpus. They are especially common in *E.Supp.*, whereas there are fewer examples in *Heraclidae*, regardless of the type of character. On the contrary, personalisation, their upgrader counterpart, has a more significant distribution per character type (See 3.2, Table 4a).

(2) The suppliants use gnomic expressions (Adrastus, Orestes and Hecuba 1 and 2), but none of them utter defocalisers, which are limited to seven characters with a higher status (Demophon, Copreus, Theseus, the Herald in *E.Supp.*, Aethra as the mother of Theseus, Menelaus in *E.Or.* and Odysseus). Thus, impersonalisation through the use of defocalisers, such as the indefinite pronoun *τις*, seems to be less indirect or off record and, consequently, does not fully work as a negative politeness strategy.

3.1.3 Forewarnings and reluctance

Politeness strategies involving apology or excuse are barely represented in the corpus, to the point that expressions of the type ‘sorry’ or ‘excuse me’ are never employed in the selected suppliant scenes. Forewarnings are only uttered by characters with a lower status (namely Hecuba 2, Aethra and Orestes).⁵ Since there are few female characters, the fact that two of them who use forewarnings are women could be telling as to the way in which female speakers need to justify their own speech acts through metacomments.

Reluctance is likewise scarcely attested in the corpus. Only Adrastus (*E.Supp.* 163–167) and Orestes (*E.Or.* 544–550; 579–580; 671–673) express reluctance to utter an FTA. It should be noted that these suppliants fail to achieve their aims

⁴ Thus, *gnomai* are generally placed at the end of the *rheseis* (Collard 1975: vol. 2, 115; Collard 1975: vol. 2, 195).

⁵ *E.Hec.* 824–825, *E.Supp.* 293–302; *E.Or.* 544–550, 559–560, 579–581, 669–671.

(Adrastus is eventually accepted only after Aethra's mediation). All this leads to the conclusion that reluctance should not probably be considered as an operative strategy, at least in Euripidean tragedy, despite the fact that it features in the typologies based on modern languages.

3.2 Distribution of upgraders

As can be seen in Table 4a, the distribution of upgraders points to even more significant differences as to the character type than the distribution of downgraders. First and foremost, upgraders are mainly uttered by characters with a higher status (Demophon, Copreus, Theseus, the Herald in *E.Supp.*, Menelaus in *E.Andr.*, Tyndareus, Peleus and Agamemnon), regardless of the participation level of each character (see Table 1, Section 2.1). Theseus and Peleus—a young and an older leader, respectively—stand out among the *supplicandi* in their use of upgraders. Yet, Copreus employs the largest number of upgraders. All the upgraders are well represented in his speech especially when considering his participation level as compared with, for instance, Theseus'.⁶

On the contrary, accepted suppliants avoid upgraders in their speech (Iolaus, Andromache and Hecuba 2), whereas rejected suppliants do indeed employ them (Adrastus, Orestes, Hecuba 1). Menelaus in *E.Or.* and Odysseus rate relatively low in their use of upgraders. Both are *supplicandi* who, as it were, diplomatically reject their respective suppliants. They are diplomatic in that they exercise their power without associating it with an on-record expression.

Table 4a. Distribution of overstaters, intensifiers, +committers, aggressive interrogatives (AIs) and personalisation (Person.) per character; column percentage per no. of coded words. No. of words in brackets.

Characters	Overstaters	Intensifiers	+Commit- ters	AIs	Person. (σύ)
Demophon (<i>Heracl.</i>)	14.23% (73)	0%	3.9% (20)	1.89% (14)	2.6% (17)
Iolaus (<i>Heracl.</i>)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Copreus (<i>Heracl.</i>)	8.97% (46)	21.81% (70)	7.8% (40)	11.23% (83)	23.89% (156)

⁶ The coverage percentages, namely, the level of Copreus' and Theseus' participation regarding the total number of words in the whole tragedy, not just the suppliant scene, as shown in Table 1, are 7.66 per cent and 21.03 per cent, respectively.

Theseus (<i>Supp.</i>)	28.07% (144)	15.26% (49)	16.57% (85)	21.79% (161)	11.49% (75)
Adrastus (<i>Supp.</i>)	6.63% (34)	4.05% (13)	1.36% (7)	0.81% (6)	3.98% (26)
Aethra (<i>Supp.</i>)	1.75% (9)	0%	7.02% (36)	2.84% (21)	0%
Herald (<i>Supp.</i>)	2.14% (11)	0%	0%	9.88% (73)	5.67% (37)
Menelaus (<i>Or.</i>)	0%	2.18% (7)	0%	2.03% (15)	0%
Orestes (<i>Or.</i>)	2.92% (15)	1.56% (5)	11.7% (60)	4.6% (34)	17.46% (114)
Tyndareus (<i>Or.</i>)	7.21% (37)	6.23% (20)	9.94% (51)	7.85% (58)	2.76% (18)
Peleus (<i>Andr.</i>)	6.24% (32)	31.46% (101)	10.14% (52)	11.64% (86)	12.4% (81)
Andromache (<i>Andr.</i>)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Molossus (<i>Andr.</i>)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Menelaus (<i>Andr.</i>)	1.36% (7)	15.58% (50)	12.87% (66)	8.93% (66)	13.78% (90)
Odysseus (<i>Hec.</i>)	6.82% (35)	0%	1.56% (8)	5.95% (44)	1.07% (7)
Hecuba 1 (<i>Hec.</i>)	6.04% (31)	1.87% (6)	13.06% (67)	7.85% (58)	3.06% (20)
Agamemnon (<i>Hec.</i>)	7.6% (39)	0%	4.09% (21)	2.71% (20)	1.84% (12)
Hecuba 2 (<i>Hec.</i>)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Finally, the lexical intensifiers (LIs), to wit, insults, are analysed with regard to three axes (see Comrie 1976): the LIs uttered by the speaker to the hearer, to something relating to the hearer, or those uttered by the speaker to another addressee against a bystander (speaker-bystander axis). Thus, a LI in the speaker-bystander axis consists in insulting a participant in the third person even when the participant can—and actually does—take part in the interaction. LIs lie at the very end of the on-record scale and this seems to be particularly the case for

those in the speaker-bystander axis.⁷ Hence, to speak of an addressee in the third person instead of addressing him/her directly when (s)he is perfectly capable of participating in the interaction is already degrading:

This occurs when it is assumed by the interlocutors in a conversation that some other person is of such an inferior status as to debar him from making a reasonable contribution. One example is the way in which many parents talk over their children; another is where interlocutors talk about people with disabilities as if they were not there (Short 1981: 194).

An example of this degrading way of interacting can be found in the 1990s BBC Radio 4 programme about disability called, *Does he take sugar?* As to Greek tragedy, this is also the case in the following exchange between Heracles and his son at the end of *Trachiniae*:

(11) (Heracles–Hyllus): ἀνὴρ ὄδ', ὡς ἕοικεν, οὐ νεμεῖν ἔμοι | φθίνοντι μοῖραν:
ἀλλὰ τοι θεῶν ἀρὰ | μενεῖ σ' ἀπιστήσαντα τοῖς ἔμοις λόγοις (S.Tr.1238–1240).

'The man will render no due respect, it seems, to my dying prayer. No, be sure that the curse of the gods will await you for disobeying my commands.' (Jebb 1883–1896)

Jebb (*ad loc.*) already remarked that "this is not an 'aside'; but the speaker's amazement precludes a direct reply".⁸

As seen in Example (11) and in Table 4b, the same phenomenon applies to the language of Greek tragedy. It is interesting to observe that LIs in the speaker-bystander axis are less common, with only four characters using them (Copreus, Theseus, Tyndareus and Menelaus in *E.Andr.*). These character are specially contentious judging by the overall distribution of upgraders and downgraders (cf. Table 3, Table 4ab). As shown in Table 4b, LIs in the speaker-bystander axis are perhaps upgraders linguistically characterising the ἐχθροί in the triangular supplication (Copreus, Tyndareus and Menelaus in *E.Andr.* are ἐχθροί).

⁷ Cf. Venegas Lagüéns (1991: 205–206): "a more serious type of direct insult is the criticism by one character to another person who is also present. The offence is, in this case, double, since the insulted party has to bear the humiliation of being observed by those present".

⁸ The expression ὡς ἕοικεν, which is in all likelihood a conventionalised ironic idiom, is discussed below (see Section 5.2).

Table 4b. Distribution of lexical intensifiers (LIs) per character; column percentage per no. of coded words. No. of words in brackets.

Characters	LI (speaker-addressee)	LI (speaker-referent)	LI (speaker-bystander)
Demophon (<i>HerACL.</i>)	1.61% (6)	0%	0%
Iolaus (<i>HerACL.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
Copreus (<i>HerACL.</i>)	24.4% (91)	17.65% (15)	60.71% (51)
Theseus (<i>Supp.</i>)	40.75% (152)	0%	8.33% (7)
Adrastus (<i>Supp.</i>)	5.9% (22)	0%	0%
Aethra (<i>Supp.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
Herald (<i>Supp.</i>)	4.29% (16)	31.76% (27)	0%
Menelaus (<i>Or.</i>)	2.41% (9)	0%	0%
Orestes (<i>Or.</i>)	3.75% (14)	17.65% (15)	0%
Tyndareus (<i>Or.</i>)	2.95% (11)	11.76% (10)	23.81% (20)
Peleus (<i>Andr.</i>)	6.97% (26)	20% (17)	0%
Andromache (<i>Andr.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
Molossus (<i>Andr.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
Menelaus (<i>Andr.</i>)	6.17% (23)	0%	7.14% (6)
Odysseus (<i>Hec.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
Hecuba 1 (<i>Hec.</i>)	0.8% (3)	1.18% (1)	0%
Agamemnon (<i>Hec.</i>)	0%	0%	0%
Hecuba 2 (<i>Hec.</i>)	0%	0%	0%

Allan (2001: 145) already observed that Copeus “is prone to insults”, quoting a number of passages (*E.Heracl.* 117, 147, 166–167, 259)—see also Yoon (2012: 110–111). What follows are examples of LIs in the speaker-bystander axis:

(12) (Copeus–Demophon / Iolaus) ἐκ τῆς ἐμαυτοῦ τούσδε δραπέτας ἔχων (*E.Heracl.* 140).⁹

‘These runaways from my country.’ (Allan 2011)

(13) (Copeus–Demophon / Iolaus) εἰ γέροντος οὔνεκα, | τύμβου,¹⁰ τὸ μηδὲν ὄντος,¹¹ ὡς εἰπεῖν ἔπος, | παίδων <τε> τῶνδ’, ἐς ἄντλον ἐμβήσῃ πόδα (*E.Heracl.* 166–168).

‘If you get into difficult waters for the sake of an ancient man, almost a tomb, a nothing, and these children!’ (Allan 2011)¹²

Wilkins (1993: 73) remarks that “the expression (τύμβου) is not only colloquial but offensive, and may serve to characterise the speaker”.¹³

4 Results

The findings of this research are twofold. From the standpoint of linguistic characterisation, the main point is that im/politeness strategies are not randomly distributed among characters: the accepted suppliants do not utter upgraders to the *supplicandi*. On the contrary, the rejected suppliants are presented, as it were, as ineffectual since they address upgraders to the *supplicandi* even though they are in a disadvantaged position and in need of requesting. In turn, the *supplicandi*

⁹ Cf. Allan (2001: 144): “runaways: with δραπέτας the Herald implies that the Hcld. are no more than runaway slaves and the property of Eur. (cf. 175–6, 267)”.

¹⁰ On the punctuation, see Wilkins 1993: 73.

¹¹ Regarding this insult, see Barrett (1964: 280) *ad E.Hipp.* 638–639 and Denniston (1939: 94) *ad E.El.* 370.

¹² See also *E.Heracl.* 171–174 (Copeus–Demophon) and Wilkins (1993: 74) *ad loc.*

¹³ For this insult as a colloquialism, see also Stevens (1976: 12): “in ancient writers on Comedy τυμβογέροντες is cited as one of the mocking terms applied to old men [...]; cf. in colloquial Latin *sepulcrum*, e.g. Plaut. *Pseud.* 412”. It should be noted that ὡς εἰπεῖν ἔπος is not a *hedge*—Copeus is firmly stating what he means. It is only in the domain of μηδέν, cf. Pearson (1907: 59): “ὡς εἰπεῖν ἔπος is a phrase of qualification here attached to τὸ μηδέν. Cf. *Hipp.* 1162 [...]. It should not be rendered by our ‘so to speak’, which is used quite differently”, cf. *LSJ s.v.* ἔπος II, 4.

barely address downgraders to the suppliants, unless they reject them. As a result, there is always a linguistic characterisation by contrast between the participants.

From a purely linguistic standpoint, this distribution sheds light, in turn, on which of the im/politeness strategies included in the typologies proposed by Brown and Levinson (1987) and by House and Kasper (1981) can be considered as such, at least in Euripidean tragedy, and on how they actually work.

5 Discussion: overpoliteness, pragmaticalisation of irony and verbal formula mismatches

Most of the analysed cases fit easily into the proposed categories, although some of these categories are underrepresented in the sample. Thus, politeness theory, as put forward by Brown and Levinson (1987), has made it possible to identify which strategies are to be regarded as such in Greek tragedy and the degree of some of them on the on- and off-record scale. However, there are several instances that could apparently be explained as downgraders but that express the opposite in highly tense and sarcastic interactions (e.g. *E.Heracl.* 257–261; *Supp.* 566–571). Three idioms stand out in this regard in the corpus: εἰ βούλη or βούλη + subj./acI ('if you want / do you want that...?'), ὡς ἔοικεν ('as it seems'), and οὐκ οἶδ' ἐγώ ('I am not aware that...'). Most significantly, these expressions perform in this way more than once in the corpus in similar contexts.¹⁴

5.1 εἰ βούλη or βούλη + subj./acI:

Let us take a look at the following example:¹⁵

(14) (Herald–Theseus) Κη. βούλη συνάψω μῦθον ἐν βραχεῖ †σέθεν†¹⁶;
| Θη. λέγ', εἴ τι βούλη· καὶ γὰρ οὐ σιγηλὸς εἶ. | Κη. οὐκ ἄν ποτ' ἐκ γῆς
παῖδας Ἀργείων λάβοις. | Θη. κάμοῦ νυν ἀντάκουσον, εἰ βούλη, πάλιν. | Κη.

¹⁴ εἰ βούλη / βούλη + subj./acI: *E.Supp.* 566–571 (x2), *E.Heracl.* 63; ὡς ἔοικεν: *E.Heracl.* 257–261, *E.Supp.* 157, *E.Andr.* 551–552, *E.Hec.* 229–230, see also Example (11); οὐκ οἶδ' ἐγώ: *E.Supp.* 518–521; *E.Hec.* 396–397. See Rodríguez-Piedrabuena (2020: 73–96) for a much more detailed discussion on overpoliteness in Euripides.

¹⁵ This seems to be a favourite example of scholars enquiring into politeness strategies in Ancient Greek, as this very same stichomythia has also been recently discussed by Emde Boas (2017) and Huitink (2018).

¹⁶ On the word σέθεν, cf. Jackson 1955: 100. Diggle (1994: 18–19) suggests τιθεῖς instead of σέθεν.

κλύοιμ' ἄν· οὐ γὰρ ἀλλὰ δεῖ δοῦναι μέρος. | Θη. θάψω νεκροὺς γῆς ἐξελθὼν Ἀσωπίας (E.*Supp.* 566–571).

‘HERALD: Do you want me to tell my story briefly? THESEUS: Say what you will; for you are not silent as it is. HERALD: You shall never take the sons of Argos from our land. THESEUS: Hear, then, my answer too to that, if you wish. HERALD: I will hear you; not that I wish it, but I must give you your turn. THESEUS: I will bury the dead, when I have removed them from Asopus’ land.’ (Coleridge 1938)

On the one hand, the structure βούλη + subjunctive could be initially considered as a pre-expansion of an adjacency pair of the type *May I ask you...?*, a conventionalised expression in English which was labelled by Leech (1983: 140) as an example of “hedged performative”. In turn, εἰ βούλη could be initially understood as a hedge relating to the felicity conditions of the type previously analysed (see Section 3.1.1). Yet, this example is far from being interpreted in such terms. As already described by Collard (1975: vol. 2, 257), the stichomythia is a piece of “cold and ironical politeness”.¹⁷

5.2 ὡς ἔοικε

The idiom ὡς ἔοικε ‘as it seems’ could apparently function as a committer, for instance in order to mitigate blunt statements. However, the contexts in which this expression recurrently appears in the corpus do not allow for such an interpretation. The idiom ὡς ἔοικε is attested up to five times and is always uttered by particularly contentious characters who elsewhere tend to use upgraders. Let us consider the following example:

(15) (Copreus–Demophon): Κη. σὺ δ’ ἐξόριζε, κῆτ’ ἐκεῖθεν ἄζομεν. | Δη. σκαιὸς πέφυκας τοῦ θεοῦ πλείω φρονῶν. | Κη. δεῦρ’, ὡς ἔοικε, τοῖς κακοῖσι φευκτέον. | Δη. ἅπασι κοινὸν ῥῆμα δαιμόνων ἔδρα. | Κη. ταῦτ’ οὐ δοκῆσει τοῖς Μυκηναίοις ἴσως (E.*Heracl.* 257–261).

‘COPREUS: Then send them beyond the frontier and we will take them from there. DEMOPHON: You are a fool to think your ideas above god. COPREUS: Here, it seems, is where the wicked should [should] seek

¹⁷ Likewise, the scholar describes κλύοιμ' ἄν (E.*Supp.* 570, cf. 465 λέγοιμ' ἄν ἦδη) as “still coldly polite”. See also Morwood (2007: 188) on εἰ βούλη: “the Greek word for ‘want’, ‘wish’, ‘am willing’, is used for the third time within four lines. But the politeness is surely ironical. These are two angry men”.

refuge. DEMOPHON: a sanctuary of the gods is a common defence for all.
COPREUS: Perhaps it will not appear so to the Mycenaeans.’ (Allan 2001)

This is exactly the same expression with which Theseus ironically addresses Adrastus (*E.Supp.* 157).¹⁸ Peleus, again a contentious character, uses this expression ironically in *E.Andr.* 551–552.¹⁹ Finally, Hecuba is a rejected suppliant who also employs the idiom ironically when addressing Odysseus (*E.Hec.* 229–230).²⁰ In light of this, we could refer back to Example (11) in which Heracles ironically employs the expression to address Hyllus when his son is unwilling to comply with his request.

5.3 οὐκ οἶδ’ ἐγώ

Finally, the expression οὐκ οἶδ’ ἐγώ ‘I am not aware that’ is found as the idioms εἰ βούλη / βούλη + subj./acI and ὡς ἔοικεν. There are two instances in the corpus, both uttered by characters with a higher status and no need for downgraders and in highly tense contexts when reacting to a bald-on-record FTA:

(16) (Theseus–Herald): οὐκ οἶδ’ ἐγὼ Κρέοντα δεσπόζοντ’ ἐμοῦ | οὐδὲ σθένοντα μεῖζον, ὅστ’ ἀναγκάσαι | δρᾶν τὰς Ἀθήνας ταῦτ’· ἄνω γὰρ ἂν ῥέοι | τὰ πράγμαθ’ οὕτως, εἰ ἴπιταξόμεσθα δῆ (*E.Supp.* 518–521).²¹
‘I am not aware that Creon is my lord and master, or that his power outweighs mine, that so he should compel Athens to act in this way; no! for then would the tide of time have to flow backward, if we are to be ordered, as he thinks.’ (Coleridge 1938).

(17) (Odysseus–Hecuba): Εκ. πολλή γ’ ἀνάγκη θυγατρὶ συνθανεῖν ἐμέ. | Οδ. πῶς; οὐ γὰρ οἶδα δεσπότης κεκτημένος (*E.Hec.* 396–397).²²
‘HECUBA: Die with my daughter I must and will. ODYSSEUS: How so? I did not know I had a master.’ (Coleridge 1938)

¹⁸ See also Allan (2001: 153) on line 261 (ταῦτ’ οὐ δοκίσει τοῖς Μυκηναίοις ἕως): “ἴσως [...] here at line end is threatening rather than tentative”.

¹⁹ On the punctuation of ὡς ἔοικε in this example, see Stevens (1971: 163).

²⁰ Note that Hecuba employs the idiom to address Agamemnon in *E.Hec.* 765–766. An ironic interpretation is also possible. However, and most importantly, this irony is not against Agamemnon but against herself.

²¹ Cf. Collard (1975: vol. 2, 248): “518–520 are a sarcastic retort to 467f.”.

²² Cf. Matthiessen (2010: 306): “vielleicht ironisch”.

A corpus language like Ancient Greek can hardly rely exclusively on postmodern approaches to politeness theory, as they focus on the evaluation of the hearer in each interaction and abhor the systematic and universalistic study of politeness (Eelen 2001; Watts 2003, Watts 2005). Still, Watts' (2005: xliii) concept of linguistic politeness as a circular continuum (see Figure 3) can better account for these seemingly puzzling examples.²³ Thus, Examples (14–17) can be understood as cases of overpoliteness, also known as mock politeness (Leech 1983, Leech 2014).²⁴

Figure 3. Politeness circular continuum model (Watts 2005: xliii, Fig.1)

²³ In any case, Brown and Levinson (1987: 248) were already aware of the limitations of their model in this very sense: “whatever politeness techniques have been especially conventionalized in a society should give rise to conventional exploitations – implicatures derived from implicatures – which would not exist in other societies without this particular conventional association. For example, [...] indirect speech acts are highly conventionalized in English [...]. Therefore, to say ‘Would you please mind not walking on the grass?’ where the context makes it clear that S[peaker] is not respecting H[earer]’s negative face [...], can implicate sarcasm or anger. We expect that such an implicature would not be available (or would be at least far more devious) in languages without highly conventionalized indirect speech acts. This factor probably accounts for much stereotypical cross-cultural misunderstanding; it represents perhaps the major limitation to universal intelligibilities in the politeness domain”. This is something barely acknowledged by the eager opponents of the theory, including Watts (2003).

²⁴ On the impact of the mismatch created by overpoliteness, see Culpeper (2011: 168): “the use of conventionalised politeness strongly mismatching a context in which a polite interpretation is not sustainable could end up exacerbating the impoliteness of the message”.

Although irony is in many cases unpredictable, there are expressions that require cognitively less effort to be interpreted as ironic than others. Examples in English include the following (Burgers and Steen 2017: 99–100): *wise guy, smart aleck, to be a bright spark, tell me about it, a likely story*, where little context is needed for the native speaker to perceive it as ironic by default. Similarly, Leech (2014: 234) compared the following examples:

(18) You're a fine friend!

(19) A fine friend *YOU* are.

(Leech 2014: 234)

The author points out that whereas (18) may or may not be ironic depending on the context, (19) “is specialized to an ironic interpretation—an example of pragmaticalisation” (see also Culpeper 2011: 167). In these instances, “recipients can immediately come to the intended meaning without having to pay attention to the propositional meaning of the irony” (Burgers and Steen 2017: 99).

The same may apply to Ancient Greek: on the one hand, there is irony entirely dependent on the context and, on the other, there is irony of a more verbal kind, which can be readily decoded. Thus, it is possible to suggest that εἰ βούλη or βούλη + subj./acI, ὡς ἔοικέ and οὐκ οἶδ' ἐγὼ are cases of conventionalised irony which are based on overpoliteness.²⁵ The three aforementioned expressions seem to be conventionalised in a similar way in which the English expressions ‘I hate to be rude’, ‘no offence’²⁶ and ‘with respect’ are. As Culpeper (2011: 177) remarked, “when one hears ‘I hate to be rude’, ‘no offence’ and ‘with respect’, there is a strong likelihood that something offensive will follow”.²⁷ Ideally, metapragmatic

²⁵ Cf. Culpeper (2011: 168): “a conventionalised politeness formula can provide such a reference point against which a conventionalised impoliteness formula or context predicting an impolite interpretation can be assessed. It alludes to a desired politeness context and in doing so provides a measure of the extreme distance by which the message flowing from the conventionalised impoliteness formula or context falls short”.

²⁶ Again ‘I hate to be rude’ and ‘no offence’ could be apparently understood as downgraders, namely, as ‘forewarnings’. However, they are conventionalised for expressing verbal mismatches.

²⁷ Who later comments on the effect of these clashes (Culpeper: 2011: 177–178): “one issue that remains is whether the mixed message devices discussed in this section actually cut deeper than non-mixed alternatives, such as simply using a conventionalised impoliteness formula. This clearly is a complex issue that depends on, amongst other things, the salience of the polite message versus the impolite message, and the context. In the case of the courtroom and Parliament, the context is

comments such as Culpeper's may shed light on the interpretation, but they are unfortunately fairly uncommon. In the absence of native-speaker intuition, the interpretation of the formulae in Sections 5.1–5.3 as being ironic by default is based on two reasons: (1) they appear more than once in similar sarcastic contexts; and (2) they are uttered by hostile characters who elsewhere employ upgraders and do not intend to rely on facework. It is also possible to assess here whether or not the hearer's reaction to them leads to an ironic interpretation, as in the case of Theseus in Example (14).

Leech (2014: 234–235) pointed out that irony “does not have to be interpreted as a proposition with a truth value”, before commenting on the idiom *Sorry I asked!*, claiming that it is a sarcastic apology “where the speaker has been humiliated for speaking out of turn”. The intonation pattern is not what would be expected, were the apology to be a sincere one. It is suggested here that the same applies to Examples (14–17). For instance, in Example (14), the Herald is not sincerely asking for a turn to speak and in all likelihood this was reflected in his intonation.

Furthermore, it should be recalled that default irony is not a more indirect way of communication and does not minimise aggressive interactions, as Leech (1983: 143–144; 2014: 236) suggested. Some scholars have proved that pragmatized or conventionalized ironic expressions require cognitively less effort to process (Burgers and Steen 2017: 98–100), as “the listener does not have to work out any implicatures”.²⁸ Katz (2017: 252) is right to note the impact of irony. Irony requires inference and implicit meaning but is not an indirect or off-record strategy just because of that (see also Pexman and Olineck 2002: 214–215). For instance, ironic criticism is not more indirect than the explicit kind. Irony is not just about flouting the sincerity of an utterance but about being insincere and somehow making it evident.²⁹

An alternative interpretation for Example (14), other than that of default irony, would be to understand it in terms of ‘verbal formula mismatches’ (Culpeper 2011: 174–178, 193), also named ‘attitude clashes’ by Leech (2014: 237–238) meaning: “an overt clash between ‘polite’ and ‘impolite’ parts of the same utterance”. Examples of verbal formula mismatches are *thank you for*

highly salient and perhaps, especially regarding the latter, primes the expectation of impoliteness”. On the use of im/politeness and overpoliteness in diplomatic contexts, see Harris (2001: 451–472).

²⁸ Alba Juez (1998: 11). See also Culpeper (2011: 177–178; 180).

²⁹ On the intention of making pretension or insincerity obvious in irony, cf. Leech (1983: 82, 142).

*nothing, Could you just fuck off?*³⁰ Yet, a preference for conventionalised irony can be seen in Theseus' reaction, as he replies with the likewise ironic εἴ τι βούλη.

In any case, Leech (2014: 238) did not rule out irony effects through verbal mismatches:

It could be claimed that attitude clash does not conform to the earlier definition of conversational irony because 'polite' and 'impolite' meanings are both overt. However, it is significant that the 'polite' piece of text tends to precede the 'impolite' piece, so that if we run through the text in real time, there is an opportunity for the target of irony to be 'led up the garden path' [...] before being forced to retrospectively reinterpret it as ironical [...] (Leech 2014: 238).

The verbal clash is obvious in the following examples:

(20) (Copreus–Iolaus) βούλη πόνον μοι τῆδε προσθεῖναι χερί; (E.*Heracl.* 63).
'Do you want to make more trouble for this hand of mine?' (Allan 2001)

(21) (Teiresias–Oedipus) εἶπω τι δῆτα κάλλ', ἵν' ὀργίζη πλέον; (S.*OT* 364).
'Should I tell you more, that you might get more angry?' (Jebb 1883–1896)

In both cases, the situation is less diplomatic and of a more domestic kind in which Copreus and Teiresias are deliberately being hostile to their addressees.³¹ Although it may surely work in a different way, there is a similar overpolite upgrader in Spanish that springs to mind. In Example (22), there also seems to be a verbal clash:

(22) — Tomaré un whisky — le dice al camarero. Y a mí—: Yo, estas mariconadas de frutas de los jóvenes, las aguas minerales de mierda esas, qué quiere que le diga ...

'I'll have a whisky,' he said to the bartender. Then in an aside to me, 'As to these faggy fruit drinks consumed by the young, those crappy mineral waters, what can I say ...'

(Francisco Casavella, *Los juegos feroces*. Barcelona: Mondadori, 2002).

³⁰ There is no consensus on the impact of the use of verbal mismatches: "there is a lack of empirical evidence as to whether such mismatches make things worse or better in the expression of negative messages" (Culpeper 2011: 167–168). See also note 27.

³¹ It has been recently suggested that Teiresias bluntly intends to make Oedipus angrier (Battezzato 2020: 204). For the concept of 'activity type' as a means of interpreting these instances, especially Example (14), see Huitink (2018).

6 Concluding remarks

In this study, we have determined the distribution of a range of politeness strategies per character type in the context of supplication. This distribution not only sheds light on the linguistic characterisation of the characters involved but has also enabled us to glimpse differences in the degree of im/politeness of some of the strategies included in the typologies proposed by Brown and Levinson (1987) and House and Kasper (1981). Hence, impersonalisation through the use of defocalisers (e.g. *τις*) seems to occupy a lower position in the politeness scale, whereas lexical intensifiers in the speaker-bystander axis appear to be located at the end of the impoliteness scale, according to their distribution per character type.

There are a number of underrepresented strategies in the corpus, namely forewarnings, reluctance and those relating to apologising. Perhaps these underrepresented politeness strategies can hardly be considered as such, at least in Euripidean tragedy, even though they are in other languages.

As a result of this analysis, we have been able to detect overpoliteness phenomena either in the form of conventionalised irony or, alternatively, as verbal formula mismatches.

The degree of im/politeness, including overpoliteness, is especially difficult to perceive in the absence of native speakers and metapragmatic comments. Once again, the distribution per character type has contributed to shed light on this issue as well as on the way in which linguistic characterisation is built in tragic language, which is otherwise relatively uniform when it comes to colloquialisms, dialectisms and other forms of linguistic variation at the level of morphology or sentence grammar.

From a broader standpoint, our purpose has been to provide a practical example of how to combine two apparently conflicting approaches to linguistic politeness, namely Brown and Levinson's and Watts', to offer a better description of the texts analysed here.³²

³² Dickey (2016) incorporates four different frameworks for understanding linguistic politeness (Brown and Levinson, Watts, Terkouraki and Hall) and concludes that, far from being exclusive, it is possible to integrate all four for a better interpretation of the data in Latin.

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